

ARIMA modelling and forecasting of malaria confirmed cases in Ondo State

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ABSTRACT

Background: Malaria is a leading cause of death especially in children under the age of 5 and still remains public health concern for Nigeria and has unique variability in specific locations, thus the need to understand the peculiarity of malaria incidence for Ondo State.

Objectives: The study seeks to understand the hidden patterns of malaria incidence in Ondo State, by applying ARIMA Model analysis to forecast malaria cases in Ondo State based on the available data for early warnings to the stakeholders in the health sector.

Methods: The data from January 2015 to December 2024 was obtained from National Malaria Elimination Programme (NMEP). The data was analysed using the ARIMA Model, selected based on a 70:30% data split ratio, with model evaluated using metrics which are root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) was used to forecast malaria cases in the State for two years.

Results: The results showed that malaria confirmed trend in the State had a sharp steady increase in malaria cases from 2016 and the highest peak reached in 2017 but it regulates down by early 2018, although a regular seasonal pattern was sustained annually. Peak seasons occur between May-June annually and forecasted malaria cases in Ondo State could go as high 9327 averagely in the next two years.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that relevant stakeholders should increase preparedness in intervention deployment against the peak seasons (May-June), to avoid resurgence of high malaria incidence in Ondo State as experienced in 2016-2017.

Keywords: Prostate ARIMA model, malaria, forecasting, Public health, trend, seasonality, interventions

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is one of the most persistent vector-borne diseases worldwide and continues to impose a significant health burden on low- and middle-income countries. Globally, the disease remains endemic in over 90 countries, with Africa bearing the heaviest burden due to its conducive ecological and climatic conditions for mosquito breeding (World Health Organization (WHO), 2023). In Nigeria, malaria accounts for a high proportion of outpatient visits and hospital admissions, contributing to increased mortality, especially among children under five years and pregnant women (Akinbobola *et al.*, 2023; Ugwu and Zewotir,

2020). Despite decades of malaria control initiatives, the disease remains a leading public health challenge.

Ondo State, in southwestern Nigeria, is one of the states with persistently high malaria prevalence, largely due to favorable rainfall patterns, warm temperatures, and vegetation cover that support mosquito vector breeding and survival (Okeke and Okafor, 2021). Malaria transmission in the state is seasonal, peaking during and shortly after the rainy season, thereby exerting pressure on the health care system. The persistent high burden of malaria cases calls for innovative tools that can predict disease trends

and guide timely interventions (Bakare *et al.*, 2024; Makinde *et al.*, 2020).

Forecasting is increasingly being recognized as a key strategy for anticipating future health care demands and enabling better allocation of scarce resources. In epidemiology, time series forecasting models are particularly important because they rely on historical surveillance data to predict future incidence (Singh *et al.*, 2024). Accurate forecasting of malaria incidence can strengthen early warning systems, improve preparedness, and enhance malaria control strategies in resource-limited settings (Makinde *et al.*, 2021).

Among forecasting approaches, the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model has become one of the most widely used statistical models for short-term disease prediction. The ARIMA model is particularly valued for its ability to capture both autocorrelations and seasonal patterns in time series data (Haruna *et al.*, 2024). Malaria incidence, which often fluctuates with climatic variables such as rainfall and temperature, provides a suitable application for ARIMA modeling (Yadav and Akhter, 2021).

Previous studies have successfully applied ARIMA models to predict malaria cases in different parts of Africa and Asia. For instance, ARIMA was used to forecast malaria incidence in Limpopo Province, South Africa, where the model showed strong accuracy in reflecting seasonal variations linked to climate (Khan *et al.*, 2024). Similarly, in China, ARIMA-based forecasts proved effective in predicting malaria dynamics and informing early interventions (Guo *et al.*, 2019). These findings highlight the model's potential in guiding control programs in malaria-endemic regions like Ondo State.

In Ondo State, reliable malaria forecasts could play a crucial role in supporting public health officials in resource planning and intervention timing. For example, predictive models can inform the stockpiling and distribution of diagnostic kits, antimalarial drugs, and insecticide-treated nets during peak seasons (Oladimeji *et*

al., 2022). This is especially vital given the limited resources available to Nigeria's health system and the urgent need to reduce malaria morbidity and mortality.

Time series models have been widely used to analyse seasonality and hidden patterns in infectious disease increase (Bakare *et al.*, 2025, Oniyelu *et al.*, 2025). By analyzing the temporal dynamics of malaria incidence, the study aims to provide scientific evidence that can strengthen malaria early warning systems. Ultimately, the findings will help policymakers design proactive interventions, optimize resource allocation, and contribute to the broader goal of malaria elimination in Nigeria (WHO, 2023).

Despite the growing body of literature on malaria epidemiology in Nigeria, there is a need to understand the peculiarity of malaria incidence over time, for specific locations of the country, given the varying spatial and climatic factors that could influence the increase in malaria incidence. The question remains that how can better preparedness to reduce malaria incidence in Ondo State be achieved. The study thus seeks to understand the hidden patterns of malaria incidence in Ondo State. This will be carried out by applying time series analysis and forecasting of malaria cases in Ondo State based on the historical. The originality of this study lies in analyzing and validating an ARIMA model based on a decade of malaria surveillance data (2015-2024) from the National Malaria Elimination Programme (NMEP). By evaluating the model with statistical metrics such as mean square error (MSE) and root mean square error (RMSE), and by generating forecasts for two subsequent years, this research contributes to the scarce yet essential body of work that bridges statistical modelling with practical malaria control. The findings provide both scientific and policy-relevant insights by highlighting the potential of predictive modelling to support early interventions, reduce disease burden, and ultimately improve public health outcomes in Ondo State and similar malaria-endemic regions.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Ondo is situated between longitudes 4° 30' and

6'' East of the Greenwich Meridian, 5° 45'' and 8° 15'' North of the equator which is located in the South- West geo-political region is bounded in the North by Ekiti and Kogi State, in the East by Edo State, in the West by Oyo and Ogun and in the South by the Atlantic Ocean (Ekpa *et al.*, 2023).

Data Description

The monthly malaria reported cases data for Ondo State, Nigeria from January 2015 to December 2024 spanning a period of 120 months were obtained from National Malaria Data Repository (NMEP). These data were the actual data from January 2015 to December 2024 which were released in January 2025 by National Malaria Data Repository (NMEP). The data did not capture year 2025 because the data for this year will be released in January 2026. The data contains malaria cases and intervention compliance count variables, of which confirmed uncomplicated malaria cases is the variable of interest for the research to focus solely on univariate time series modelling and forecasting.

ARIMA Model

A time series analysis approach called Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) which examines the autocorrelation between a data set's current observations and its historical observational values was used to analyse the data. Although, there is a strong annual seasonal pattern from the observed time series, the choice of ARIMA model over Seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA) was due to the stronger influence of trend on the observed time series than seasonal. Stationarity is tested using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test before carrying out the ARIMA model selection. The ADF value before differencing is -2.7832 with p-value of 0.2513 and after first differencing, the ADF value is -5.4286 with p-value of 0.01. For stationarity to be obtained, the p – value must be less than or equal to 0.05. The stationarity was obtained after first differencing, thus the Autocorrelation function (ACF) and Partial autocorrelation function (PACF) was also checked

before and then training of the model on a train-set which was done based on 70% and 30% data split ratio. The fitness of the model to data was tested based on the selected ARIMA values by lower Akaike information criterion (AIC) and thus make ARIMA models to get better forecasting model.

ResultsThe results of ARIMA Model using time series analysis are presented in the Figures 1 to 2 and the Tables.

Figure 1: Time series plot of the confirmed malaria cases in Ondo State

Figure 2: Seasonal and Trend LOESS (STL) decomposition of the confirmed malaria cases

Figure 3: ACF to get Autoregression

Figure 4: PACF to get Moving Average

Table 1: Training with 70% and 30%

TRAINING SET	AIC	RMSE	MAPE
ARIMA (3,1,3)	1594.22	3247.69	13.29
ARIMA (2,1,3)	1593.73	3285.59	13.58
ARIMA (2,1,4)	1594.52	3257.01	13.56

Table 2: Testing of the three selected Models on the test set

Test Set (ARIMA)	Type	Full Order (p,d,q)(P,D,Q)\s	Seasonal Period	RMSE
ARIMA (3,1,3)	Non- Seasonal	SARIMA (3,1,3) (0,0,0)\s ₅₋₆	May- June	2636.76
ARIMA (2,1,3)	Non- Seasonal	SARIMA (2,1,3) (0,0,0)\s ₅₋₆	May- June	2526.80
ARIMA (2,1,4)	Non- Seasonal	SARIMA (2,1,4) (0,0,0)\s ₅₋₆	May- June	2616.83

Table 3: ARIMA (2,1,3) Compare to test Set

Time (Months)	test_ts	forecast mean Value	Lo 80% CI	Hi 80% CI.	Lo 95% CI	HI 95% CI
Jan 2022	9260	10975.91181	6739.972636	15211.85	4497.602	17454.22
Feb. 2022	8686	11037.837	4840.826088	17234.85	1560.327	20515.35
March 2022	8252	11890.71059	4270.533477	19510.89	236.6554	23544.77
April 2022	8994	11278.65487	1744.583096	20812.73	-3302.45	25859.76
May 2022	13662	11001.16579	260.3911413	21741.94	-5425.43	27427.76
June 2022	14233	11673.08616	55.19645389	23290.98	-6094.94	29441.12
July 2022	13512	11451.50055	-1358.312962	24261.31	-8139.42	31042.42
Aug. 2022	10517	11060.97546	-2753.29959	24875.25	-10066.1	32188.09
Sept. 2022	8163	11495.57348	-3047.702114	26038.85	-10746.4	33737.59
Oct. 2022	8359	11520.82314	-3903.418477	26945.06	-12068.5	35110.17
Nov. 2022	10051	11157.03449	-5135.218351	27449.29	-13759.8	36073.89
Dec. 2022	7790	11376.83762	-5580.567963	28334.24	-14557.3	37310.95
Jan 2023	7930	11522.41995	-6149.660665	29194.5	-15504.7	38549.53
Feb. 2023	6151	11250.8208	-7178.921796	29680.56	-16935	39436.68
March 2023	6830	11313.69656	-7742.10145	30369.49	-17829.6	40457.02
April 2023	10272	11489.15928	-8185.284815	31163.6	-18600.3	41578.62
May 2023	13878	11323.1946	-9019.089789	31665.48	-19787.6	42434.03
June 2023	12438	11292.52236	-9642.893559	32227.94	-20725.4	43310.48
July 2023	13275	11445.31854	-10050.15283	32940.79	-21429.2	44319.81
Aug. 2023	12330	11369.02668	-10723.19216	33461.25	-22418.1	45156.16
Sept. 2023	9672	11297.30705	-11355.86059	33950.47	-23347.7	45942.34
Oct. 2023	10118	11405.55422	-11769.27942	34580.39	-24037.3	46848.4
Nov. 2023	9748	11391.43525	-12325.30821	35108.18	-24880.2	47663.06
Dec. 2023	7664	11314.2869	-12931.49763	35560.07	-25766.4	48395.01
Jan 2024	8896	11376.45483	-13363.22484	36116.13	-26459.6	49212.53
Feb. 2024	8799	11397.06793	-13842.7848	36636.92	-27204	49998.09
March 2024	10270	11333.81431	-14404.52532	37072.15	-28029.6	50697.21
April 2024	11814	11359.07461	-14850.75681	37568.91	-28725.4	51443.55
May 2024	14064	11392.93529	-15285.22184	38071.09	-29407.8	52193.66
June 2024	13220	11350.42275	-15798.1461	38498.99	-30169.7	52870.58
July 2024	15482	11351.41987	-16248.93549	38951.78	-30859.7	53562.52
Aug. 2024	13637	11384.71879	-16659.18573	39428.62	-31504.7	54274.17
Sept. 2024	12032	11361.9569	-17127.41527	39851.33	-32208.8	54932.69
Oct. 2024	12677	11350.37432	-17572.60981	40273.36	-32883.5	55584.26
Nov. 2024	12165	11376.19564	-17970.4051	40722.8	-33505.6	56257.95
Dec. 2024	8765	11368.41427	-18401.97805	41138.81	-34161.5	56898.3

Note: C.I means Confidence Interval

Figure 5: The Forecast of ARIMA (2,1,3) Model

Table 4: The table showing the Forecast values of ARIMA (2,1,3) Model

Date	Mean Forecast	Lower 80% Confidence Interval	Upper 80% Confidence Interval	Lower 95% Confidence Interval	Upper 95% Confidence Interval
Jan 2025	9327.288	5552.819	13101.76	3554.735	15099.84
Feb 2025	9115.833	3588.633	14643.03	662.7092	17568.96
March 2025	7751.874	884.856	14618.89	-2750.32	18254.07
April 2025	8804.411	239.3109	17369.51	-4294.78	21903.6
May 2025	9237.351	-398.672	18873.37	-5499.67	23974.38
June 2025	8099.793	-2340.4	18539.99	-7867.11	24066.69
July 2025	8480.827	-3030.19	19991.84	-9123.75	26085.4
Aug 2025	9162.472	-3247.11	21572.05	-9816.34	28141.29
Sept. 2025	8411.946	-4656.18	21480.07	-11574	28397.92
Oct. 2025	8340.456	-5519.47	22200.38	-12856.5	29537.38
Nov. 2025	8998.533	-5643.51	23640.57	-13394.5	31391.6
Dec. 2025	8632.184	-6608.42	23872.78	-14676.3	31940.67
Jan 2026	8332.012	-7548.37	24212.39	-15954.9	32618.96
Feb. 2026	8824.41	-7740.62	25389.44	-16509.6	34158.44
March. 2026	8751.426	-8378.12	25880.97	-17445.9	34948.8
April 2026	8397.04	-9284.52	26078.61	-18644.6	35438.66
May 2026	8685.224	-9599.12	26969.57	-19278.3	36648.72
June 2026	8788.218	-10032.7	27609.15	-19995.9	37572.34
July 2026	8486.786	-10833.7	27807.29	-21061.4	38034.94
Aug 2026	8597.315	-11260	28454.61	-21771.8	38966.43
Sept. 2026	8771.768	-11594	29137.55	-22375	39918.55
Oct. 2026	8569.078	-12263.1	29401.25	-23291	40429.14
Nov. 2026	8557.627	-12760.3	29875.55	-24045.3	41160.58
Dec. 2026	8730.281	-13067.2	30527.73	-24606	42066.61

Figure 3 indicates that Autocorrelation Function (ACF) which helps to suggest the order of the moving average part (q) which is 3 because it is the third line that first came out of the boundary. Similarly, figure 4 proves that Partial Autocorrelation function (PACF) which suggest the order of autoregressive part (p) is 3 as well because it is the third line that first came out of the boundary. Since the stationarity was obtained after first differencing, it means d is 1, this led to the initial guess of ARIMA (3,1,3)

from the formula ARIMA (p,d,q).

Discussion

The time series plot of the data indicates that there was a sharp increase in malaria cases in Ondo state between 2016 and 2018 as shown in figure 1. When the data was decomposed using STL as contained in figure 2, it was observed that the various components of the time series are seasonal, the trend and the remainder (noise

or error) in the data. The trend has a stronger influence on the observed time series although, there is also a significant level of noise and a regular seasonal pattern observed. From the trend, it is observed that there is a sharp steady increase in malaria cases from 2016 and the highest peak is reached in 2017, after which a steady decline is observed which regulates down by early 2018 (Figure 2). Malaria cases in Ondo show highest peak cases in the second quarter (May -June) annually. Stationarity was obtained after first differencing, the ACF and PACF were checked in order to get the assumed initial observed ARIMA Model parameters as ARIMA (3,1,3) as shown in figure 3 and figure 4 respectively. Thus, the model is trained on the data using this initial ARIMA Model. Auto-ARIMA is also used to select three best ARIMA Model based on the training sets as shown in table 1. After testing the three selected models on the test set as shown in table 2, the best fitting model is ARIMA (2,1,3) and comparing RMSE of the three models as seen in table 3, it also has the lowest RMSE of 2526.80 (table 2). Comparing ARIMA (2,1,3) to test Set as contains in table 3 further confirms that ARIMA (2,1,3) is best model. Now we forecast using best Model ARIMA (2,1,3) as shown in figure 5. The results as shown in table 4 show that malaria cases in Ondo State can go as high 9327 in the next two years with confidence interval (C.I). Hence, the relevant stakeholders should increase preparedness in their interventions on malaria control before the peak seasons (May-June), to avert the impending calamity that malaria may cause to the people in Ondo State.

Conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest in this study

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